

SoildiverAgro project

Adoption of new management practices to increase crop production and quality

THE WHAT AND WHY

No-tillage system supports earthworm communities

Tillage is known to have negative impact on earthworms by destroying their burrows, changing their food accessibility and injuring them directly. No-tillage system is an agricultural management practice where field crops are grown without disturbing the soil through tillage. By not tilling the soil, plant residues accumulate on the soil surface forming a mulch layer, which prevents the soil from drying out during periods of low precipitation and provides food source for earthworm species which feed on plant residues on the surface of the soil. Comparing conventional tillage (mouldboard ploughing) to no-tillage in Estonian case study on a Gleyic Luvisol soil, we found that earthworm abundance tended to be higher on the no-tillage field and this system supported higher abundance of anecic species, which are known to be the most sensitive towards

tillage. While earthworm communities on conventional tillage fields were dominated by species which are the most tolerant to agricultural management. On the fields where intensive tillage is used the number of earthworm species is significantly lower, which can have detrimental consequences for soil functioning since earthworm species differ in their role in supporting soil processes. Earthworms improve soil functioning by making large channels that improve water movement, burrowing activities that result in mixing the soil, breaking down plant residues into smaller parts and contributing to the formation of soil aggregates protecting soil organic matter. Therefore, applying agricultural practices which support earthworm communities is important to maintain soil quality.

1. A picture of an earthworm. Photo Shanskiy, M.

2.No-tillage field in Tartu county, Estonia. Photo Sutri, M.

KEYWORDS

Earthworms, tillage systems, no-tillage

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